

Supplementary Appendix

All genome sequences and associated metadata supporting the findings of this study can be accessed through the persistent digital object identifier

<https://doi.org/10.55876/gis8.260610gh>

In addition to the minted DOI, GISAID also communicates the aggregation of GISAID accession numbers (EPI_ISL_IDs) through the corresponding EPI_SET_260610gh identifier to facilitate both, the acknowledgment of all data contributors and the direct retrieval of the underlying data from GISAID used in this study.

hCoV-19 Virus Data Summary

GISAID Identifier	Digital Object Identifier	Number of individual viruses	Data Collection range	Number of countries/territories
EPI_SET_260610gh	https://doi.org/10.55876/gis8.260610gh	1,274	2020-12-23 to 2025-06-16	1